

A COMPUTATIONAL TOOL FOR THE ANALYSIS AND DESIGN OF STRUCTURAL ADHESIVE JOINTS

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1 Introduction

The field structural adhesive bonding is gaining more and more the interest of researchers and design engineers, due to the advantages it offers compared to other joining techniques, e.g. mechanical fastening. However, the margin of confidence regarding their mid- and long- term response is small and thus practical joints are overdesigned towards reducing in-service uncertainties.

Adhesion between composite and metals or composites and composites can be formed by two ways, with respect to the adhesive media utilized for the creation of the bondline. The first technique involves direct impregnation of the fibers on the metal substrates [1]. The main disadvantage is that a composite's resin is generally not designated for structural adhesive bonding, and thus may eventually lead to a weak bond characterized by low shear strength and fracture toughness. On the other hand, with the continuous growth of the chemical industry, more and more adhesives are being produced that are designated for structural adhesive bonding between dissimilar materials. Either in the form of films or paste systems, toughened adhesives are preferred because they present high Mode II fracture toughness (shear) [2]. Even when used as thin layers, their elastoplastic material response has proven to increase the joints' performance under static or fatigue loading conditions.

Interfacial fracture mechanics have proven to be a very promising approach for the study of the bi-material composite/adhesive or adhesive/metal interface or for the study of cohesive cracking. Likewise, the loading and fracture response of the entire bondline can be treated as an interphase between the two substrates, which involves the interfaces and the continuum adhesive layer, where all types of material behaviors and damages occur, i.e. elastic – plastic response, cohesive cracks and

interfacial debonding [3]. Considering the interphase as the area which holds together the two materials through normal and tangential tractions, then the aforementioned loading and failure mechanisms can be safely described by a phenomenological cohesive law or a traction-separation law [4]. A cohesive law combines damage mechanics (failure is based on stress considerations - Inglis) and fracture mechanics (failure is based on energy considerations - Griffith). Cohesive laws have been widely used in finite element methods for the prediction of the failure response of structural adhesive joints.

The trapezoidal model shown in Fig. 1 has proven to be a promising idealized cohesive law for modeling the loading and fracture response of adhesive joints, formed with a toughened adhesive layer when the later is deformed under pure or/and mixed-mode conditions [5].

Fig. 1. Trapezoidal cohesive model used for modeling toughened adhesive layers which present ductile behaviour (taken from [5]).

Recent works on Mode I [6] and Mode II [7] experimental characterization of the bondline revealed the real shape and characteristics of the corresponding traction-separation law ($\sigma_i - \delta_i$, $i = I$ for Mode I and II for Mode II). The aim of this work is to present a recently developed phenomenological traction-separation law and its potential for

providing numerical predictions of adhesively bonded composite-to-metal joints.

2 Phenomenological traction-separation model

2.1 Definition of pure mode laws

On an effort to obtain a mathematical description of the cohesive law that characterizes a bondline, respective experimental findings were considered. Ji et al. in [6] and Leffler et al. in [7] tested adhesively bonded Double Cantilever Beam (DCB) and End Notch Flexure (ENF) geometries, as shown in Fig. 2, aiming at measuring Mode I and Mode II fracture properties of the bondline, respectively.

Fig. 2. Fracture characterization tests for obtaining Mode I and Mode II cohesive laws of a thin adhesive layer through DCB [6] (a) and ENF [7] (b) geometries, respectively. Dimensions in mm.

In both cases the J -integral approach was utilized for the derivation of the pure mode cohesive laws, which are plotted in Fig. 3 as discrete data points. It is evident that they both describe the Fracture Process Zone (FPZ), as denoted by their intrinsic stress increase part up to a critical level followed by a softening part down to zero, where afterwards the crack is propagating by leaving behind traction free crack faces. The initial part is characterized by a non-linear response, and refers to the elastoplastic

material behaviour of the adhesive material. The trapezoidal law describes this behaviour with a bi-linear model (see Fig. 1, linear elastic perfectly plastic).

Fig. 3. Experimental traction-separation laws fitted by idealized cohesive models and the proposed phenomenological model; Mode I obtained from DCB (a) and Mode II obtained from ENF (b).

On an effort to provide a more realistic description of the elastoplastic response, the exponential function (see Eq. 1) seemed to provide best fittings to the experimental laws of Fig. 2. Additionally, this exact function is convenient for formulating the mixed-mode cohesive model as it will be shown afterwards.

$$\sigma_i(\delta_i) = \sigma_{c,i} - \sigma_{c,i} \exp\left(-\frac{\delta_i k_i}{\sigma_{c,i}}\right) \quad (1)$$

where $\sigma_{c,i}$ is the critical stress and k_i is the initial slope; both magnitudes can be experimentally defined. This exponential form has a horizontal asymptote at $\sigma_{c,i}$ and thus the actual critical stress $\sigma_{c,i}(1-e)$ defined at the corresponding abscissa $\delta_{0,i}$ can be obtained from the following equation:

$$\delta_{0,i} = -\frac{\ln(e) \sigma_{c,i}}{k_i} \quad (2)$$

where e is a parameter denoting the difference of the actual critical stress and the asymptote. In the regime where tractions descend ($\delta_{0,i} - \delta_{c,i}$), a linear function is used as with the trapezoidal law and expressed herein by:

$$\sigma_i(\delta_i) = -\frac{(1-e)\sigma_{c,i}}{\delta_{c,i} - \delta_{0,i}} \delta_i + \frac{(1-e)\sigma_{c,i}\delta_{c,i}}{\delta_{c,i} - \delta_{0,i}} \quad (3)$$

where $\delta_{c,i}$ is the critical separation where tractions become zero.

Eq. (1) – Eq. (3) were used to obtain the proposed expo-linear law out from the experimental data sets in Fig. 3. In Fig. 3a the trapezoidal and triangular idealized laws were additionally fitted, by maintaining the same basic cohesive parameters ($\sigma_{c,i}$ and J_{ci}). The extrinsic trapezoidal and triangular cohesive laws shown in Fig. 3b were obtained from Eq. (1) – Eq. (3) by controlling k_i and e . This demonstrates the flexibility of the shape of the proposed law.

The obtained expo-linear laws were generalized so they can be utilized for the description of the constitutive response of cohesive elements, as shown in Fig. 4. A penalty contact was utilized in the Mode I law (see Fig. 4a), which is activated when $\delta_1 < 0$ for avoiding element interpenetration. The Mode II cohesive law (see Fig. 4b) evolves the same for $\delta_1 > 0$ and $\delta_1 < 0$, but with opposite sign tractions. The linear and trapezoidal laws are treated likewise [5].

2.2 Validation of pure mode laws

The expo-linear law together with the triangular and trapezoidal laws were further used for the back calculation of the global response ($P - \delta^*$) of the

DCB and ENF tests, through finite element simulations. The entire bondline was modeled with quadratic cohesive elements and the traction-separation laws of Fig. 3 (expo-linear as in Fig. 4 in FEA) were used as their constitutive relation, respectively. These were programmed in a user element subroutine (UEL) in Abaqus commercial software. The obtained results are compared together with the experimental ones taken from [6] and [7] for the DCB and ENF, respectively, in Fig. 5. Magnitude P corresponds to the applied force and magnitude δ^* corresponds to the pre-crack tip normal separation for the Mode I test (DCB) and to the pre-crack tip sliding separation for the Mode II test (ENF).

Fig. 4. Proposed EPZ laws for the prediction of Mode I (a) and Mode II or III (b) loading and fracture.

The significant difference between the experimental and numerical propagation part in Fig. 5a, does not affect our conclusions regarding the numerical

results. It is clear that regardless the choice of the cohesive law shape, the predictions present the same crack propagation response in both tests, denoting that the effect of the detailed cohesive law shape is insignificant for the considered bondlines, as long as the toughness and the critical stress are maintained equal for all models. However, there is a small influence to the initial loading part prior to crack propagation, which was expected according to previous studies.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 5. Force P – precrack tip separation δ^* as experimentally measured and numerically predicted from the DCB (a) and ENF (b) geometries shown in Fig. 2.

The next step is to combine the proposed pure mode traction-separation laws under a framework that

accounts their interdependency through damage and fracture mechanics. This is appropriate for modeling practical adhesive joints, where all loads and moments acting on the joints' substrates lead the adhesive layer to deform and fail under mixed-mode conditions.

2.3 Formulation of mixed-mode model

The expo-linear phenomenological laws have been formulated under a mixed-mode model (see Fig. 6) for modeling 2D problems (Mode I and II) in [4] and 3D problems (Mode I, II and III) in [8].

Fig. 6. Exponential-linear mixed-mode cohesive model ($i = I, II$ and III).

Damage initiation occurs when the quadratic stress criterion is met, whereas damage propagation occurs when the linear energetic criterion is satisfied. The derivation of the mixed-mode cohesive parameters was driven through the mode mixities:

$$\beta_{II} = \frac{\delta_{II}}{\delta_I} \quad \text{and} \quad \beta_{III} = \frac{\delta_{III}}{\delta_I} \quad (4)$$

and the resultant total separation δ_m :

$$\delta_m = \sqrt{\delta_I^2 + \delta_{II}^2 + \delta_{III}^2} \quad (5)$$

By combining the stress and energy criterion together with Eq. (2), (4) and (5), one can obtain the mixed mode cohesive parameters of the decoupled pure mode laws, i.e. $\sigma_{cm,i}$, $\delta_{0m,i}$, $\delta_{cm,i}$ and J_i , for a given mode-mixity at a material point laying on the modeled interface.

3 Validation of the 2D and 3D mixed-mode model

For the validation of the 2D model, steel-to-steel adhesively bonded geometries have been fabricated and tested. A Single Lap Joint (SLJ) and a Double Strap Joint (DSJ), have been found to be good candidates for validation purposes, since both are widely used and the adhesive is stressed under different mixed-mode conditions in each geometry [4]. For validating the 3D model a simple geometry should be considered that stresses the adhesive layer in peel (Mode I), in-plane shear (Mode II) and out-of-plane shear (Mode III). Thus a SLJ configuration subjected to eccentric loading, namely SLJ-EL, was designed [9].

In all three geometries the substrates were manufactured from normal steel whereas the adhesive material was a toughened epoxy adhesive, that is Araldite 2015. The adhesive thickness was 0.5 mm for the SLJ and DSJ cases and with 0.8 mm for the SLJ-EL. The joints were tested under uniaxial static tension and during the tests the force P and the applied displacement u were recorded.

The geometries were modeled in Abaqus and quadratic plane and solid elements, were utilized for the substrates of the SLJ/DSJ and SLJ-EL geometries, respectively. The entire bondline was modeled with quadratic cohesive elements and their constitutive response was represented by the Expo-Linear model shown in Fig. 6.

The cohesive parameters were taken equal to the properties provided by the adhesive's manufacturer. Thus, k_i is defined as the ratio between the Young modulus - E (Mode I) or shear modulus - G (Mode II and III) over the adhesive thickness. Magnitudes $\sigma_{c,I}$ and $\sigma_{c,II}$ (and $\sigma_{c,III}$) are taken equal to the strength of the adhesive in tension and shear, respectively. Magnitudes $\delta_{0,i}$ are calculated analytically through Eq. (2).

Fig. 7 presents a comparison between the experimentally measured and numerically calculated $P-u$ global response. Additionally, the SLJ and DSJ were modeled with the trapezoidal model as shown in Fig. 7a and Fig. 7b, respectively. An overall assessment of the results indicates that the proposed model captures very accurately the nonlinear loading and strength of the considered joints, whereas the

trapezoidal misses to capture the detailed non-linearities.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Fig. 7. Validation of the mixed-mode model with SLJ (a), DSJ (b) and SLJ-EL (c) geometries, by comparing the experimental global response with the respective obtained numerical predictions.

4 Analysis of composite-to-metal adhesively joint geometries

4.1 Flat adherents

Having the model validated, two classical laboratory and also practical geometries have been considered for analysis, i.e. CFRP-to-steel SLJ and DLJ adhesively bonded joints, presented in Fig. 8. These geometries have been tested under uniaxial static tension and the results are reported in [10] and [11] for the SLJs and DLJs, respectively.

Their corresponding modeling and simulation is based on the exponential-linear EPZ model of Fig. 6, since both geometries involve a toughened adhesive material that presents a ductile elasto-plastic material response. The motivation for such simulations was to calculate the load carrying capacity and the peel/ shear stress distributions over the adhesive area, over the loading history.

Fig. 8. Composite-to-steel adhesive joints modeled with the proposed mixed-mode model. Subplot (a) and (b) present SLJ and Double Lap Joint (DLJ) with flat adherents, respectively.

For the SLJs, seven cases were considered which have different geometric parameters, that is two different adhesive thicknesses t_a (0.5 mm or 0.85 mm), two different overlap lengths L_o (25 mm or 75 mm) and two different stiffness ratios that result to different substrate thicknesses t_s (5 mm and 8 mm) and t_c (8 mm or 10 mm). Fig. 9 presents a comparison of the experimentally measured and numerically predicted failure of these joints. For the joints with short overlap 25 mm (SLJ-5, SLJ-6 and SLJ-7) the prediction is within 2.2% of the experimental value, whereas for the long overlap 75 mm joints (SLJ-1, SLJ-2, SLJ-3 and SLJ-4) the prediction is within 25% of the respective experimental value. This is because the mechanics

of the short overlap joints is such, that the entire adhesive layer enters plasticity ($\sigma_{c,II}$ is reached by all material points of the EPZ) at the failure load level (see Fig. 10a). After that point the joints fail. On the other hand, predictions of the joints with 75mm overlap denote a more complex stress field distribution over the adhesive area prior to failure (see Fig. 10b and 10c). This is more intense for the SLJ-3 and SLJ-4 cases, where the steel substrate develops plastic deformations at the overlap edge, and thus severe stress redistributions are calculated over the adhesive as shown in Fig. 10c. Additionally the plastic hinge developed at the steel substrates affects the peel and out-of-plane shear stresses, as calculated with the proposed EPZ model. However, it seems that such stress field does not affect significantly the joints' failure load.

Fig. 9. Experimental and numerical failure loads for all SLJ cases considered [12].

The analysis of the CFRP-to-steel DLJs (see Fig. 8b) is reported in [13], for the 6 different cases considered, which differ in the overlap length (20 or 38 mm), in the width (19, 26.8 or 38 mm) and the steel thickness (6.05 mm or 1.6 mm). Likewise, these tested cases were simulated by modeling the adhesive layer with cohesive elements and utilizing the proposed EPZ model of Fig. 6 as their constitutive response. Fig. 11 compares the experimentally measured and numerically predicted failure loads of the six cases.

Fig. 10. Variation of in-plane shear stresses of SLJ with 25 mm overlap length (a) and with 75 mm overlap length (b) and (c), as calculated at the maximum failure load. Note that subplot (b) refers to the joints that remain in the elastic region whereas subplot (c) refers to the joints that steel deforms plastically.

Additionally, FEA of predictions of the failure load is shown with the use of the Damage Zone Theory (DZT), reported in [11]. It can be seen that better predictions are obtained with the EPZ model for the A04 – A06 cases compared to the DZT. However, more interesting is to have an insight into the stress variations along the bondline, that are eventually responsible for the loading and failure response of the joints. As shown in Fig. 12, the adhesive layer of case A01 that has a 38 mm overlap compared to case A04 that has a 20 mm overlap, fails progressively after a certain area has entered plasticity.

Fig. 11. Experimental and numerical failure loads for all DLJ cases considered [13].

Fig. 12. Normalized shear stress distributions over the adhesive layer of two DLJ cases [13].

This can be seen by comparing the shear stress states at level e, which stands for the late stage damage propagation occurring at the failure load level.

4.2 Tubular adherents

The aim of the parametric study is to yield conclusions regarding the effect of various geometric and material parameters to the behaviour and strength of the adopted adhesive joint cases, which are subjected to combined internal pressure and axial loading. The operational pressure of 10 bar has been kept constant for all cases, while the axial strength of the joints (ultimate applied force - F_u) was calculated.

In all three adhesive joints (Fig. 13 a, b and c) six values of the overlap length L_o have been considered, as follows:

- 20 mm
- 40 mm
- 60 mm
- 80 mm
- 100 mm
- 120 mm

As far as the SLJ cases are concerned, the L_o magnitude is the unique parameter investigated. However, for the tube-to-tube and the tube-to-flange SSJ adhesive joint cases the effect of strap material and thickness t_s have been also considered in the parametric study. The two materials selected for the strap are the following:

- CFRP (the same as the tube material)
- Aluminum

and the two strap thicknesses are the following:

- 4 mm
- 8 mm.

Hence, 24 cases have been considered for the tube-to-tube and tube-to-flange SSJ geometries (6 overlap lengths x 2 materials x 2 strap thicknesses) and 6 cases for the tube-to-tube SLJ geometries.

Fig. 14, presents a comparison of the maximum attained load (strength), as numerically predicted for all considered cases of the SLJ and SSJ tube-to-tube adhesive joint geometries. It must be noted that the overlap length L_o in the SSJ cases is the half length of the strap material, according to Fig.13.

The strength predictions are approximately equal for all considered cases and for L_o values less than 80 mm. Regardless the case considered, the trend of the global response curve denotes a behaviour of the

strength tending to a plateau as of the overlap length increases. This behaviour is obvious for L_o values higher than 100 mm and particularly for the SSJ cases that have an 8 mm thick strap. The existence of a plateau beyond which the strength of lap joints does not increase with further increase in the overlap length, is a common characteristic of adhesive joints with flat adherents.

Fig. 13: Tube-to-tube SLJ (a) and SSJ (b) geometries and tube-to-flange SSJ (c) geometry adopted in the numerical parametric study (all dimensions in mm).

Fig. 15 presents a comparison of the global force-displacement responses as numerically calculated for the six different overlap lengths, for the tube-to-tube SLJ geometry and for a typical SSJ geometry. In reality, each curve begins from zero; however, for reasons of clarity, the curves have been shifted between each other by 0.4 mm. According to this figure, the trend of the predicted global response is characterized non-linear for small overlap lengths and turns into linear as the overlap length increases,

particularly in the typical SSJ case of Fig. 16b. This behaviour is totally attributed to the exponential traction increasing part of the proposed EPZ laws, which describes the elastoplastic region of the ductile adhesive material utilized.

Thus, in the cases where a relatively small overlap length is utilized, the entire adhesive layer contributes to the stress development and subsequently enters plasticity at the same time leading to sudden failure.

Fig. 14. Comparison of the maximum attained forces from all tube-to-tube SLJ and SSJ cases.

Fig. 15. Global response of the SLJ (a) and SSJ (b) tube-to-tube cases. The curves have been shifted by 0.4 mm for clarity.

4 Conclusions

This work presents a new mixed-mode cohesive model designated for the prediction of the loading and fracture response of toughened adhesive layers used for the design of structural adhesive joints. The new model has been initially validated and verified with laboratory metal-to-metal and metal-to-composite geometrical configuration, i.e. single lap and double strap joints. It has been shown herein that the proposed model is able to capture experimental global responses and provide predictions of the stress field developed over the bondline through the loading history. It can be concluded that such computational tool is promising for the analysis and design of adhesive joints that involve similar or dissimilar adherents.

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